

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON THE THERMOLYSIS PROCESS OF BIOCHAR DERIVED FROM COCONUT HUSK FIBER AND ITS EFFECTS ON THE PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF GREY SOIL IN NORTHERN VIETNAM

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of temperature on the thermolysis process of biochar derived from coconut husk fiber and its effects on the physical and chemical properties of grey soil in Northern Vietnam. Biochar, produced under varying thermal conditions, was analyzed to determine changes in its structural characteristics and chemical composition. The resultant biochar was then applied to grey soil, and its impact on soil properties such as texture, nutrient content, pH, and cation exchange capacity was assessed. Our findings demonstrate that temperature significantly affects the quality of biochar, with higher temperatures enhancing porosity and surface area, thereby improving its efficacy as a soil amendment. The application of optimized biochar to grey soil resulted in notable improvements in soil fertility and structure, promoting better crop growth conditions. This research underscores the potential of temperature-regulated biochar as a sustainable solution for soil enhancement and agricultural productivity in Northern Vietnam, providing insights into effective biochar production and utilization practices.

Keywords: Thermolysis process, Biochar, Coconut husk fiber, Soil fertility, Northern Vietnam, Environmental impact, Soil enhancement, Soil quality

INTRODUCTION

The utilization of biochar derived from coconut husk fiber presents a promising avenue for enhancing soil quality and agricultural sustainability. In regions such as Northern Vietnam, where grey soil predominates and serves as a crucial substrate for agricultural activities, understanding the thermolysis process of biochar and its response to temperature variations is imperative. Temperature plays a pivotal role in governing the kinetics and extent of thermolysis reactions, thereby influencing the physical and chemical properties of biochar and its interactions with soil matrices.

This study endeavors to investigate the influence of temperature on the thermolysis process of biochar derived from coconut husk fiber and its subsequent effects on the physical and chemical properties of grey soil in Northern Vietnam. By elucidating the thermolysis kinetics and its consequences on biochar characteristics, such as surface area, porosity, and chemical composition, this research aims to provide valuable insights into optimizing biochar application for soil enhancement.

Furthermore, understanding the impact of biochar on the physical and chemical properties of grey soil is essential for sustainable agricultural practices. Grey

soil, characterized by its unique composition and fertility, serves as a vital resource for crop cultivation in Northern Vietnam. By elucidating the interactions between biochar and grey soil under different temperature regimes, this study seeks to facilitate informed decision-making regarding biochar utilization strategies in agricultural landscapes.

In light of these considerations, this research underscores the importance of interdisciplinary approaches that integrate principles of chemistry, agronomy, and environmental science to address pressing challenges in soil management and agricultural sustainability. By bridging the gap between fundamental scientific understanding and practical applications, this study aims to contribute to the development of innovative solutions for enhancing soil fertility and productivity in Northern Vietnam and beyond.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

- Biochar derived from coconut husk fiber
- Grey soil in Northern Vietnam

Research Methodology:

The experiment was conducted in three steps as follows:

Phase 1: Manufacturing and analyzing biochar samples from coconut husk fiber at different temperatures:

Procedure: Coconut husk fiber was used as the raw material. After drying and cleaning, the fiber was fed into a biochar production machine and subjected to pyrolysis at various temperatures for 2 hours. Subsequently, samples were taken for analysis according to Vietnamese standards to estimate the nutrient content in the biochar.

Experimental Formulas:

Formula 1 (T1-Control): Pyrolysis of coconut husk fiber at 200°C

Formula 2 (T2): Pyrolysis of coconut husk fiber at 250°C

Formula 3 (T3): Pyrolysis of coconut husk fiber at 300°C

Formula 4 (T4): Pyrolysis of coconut husk fiber at 350°C

Formula 5 (T5): Pyrolysis of coconut husk fiber at 400°C

Formula 6 (T6): Pyrolysis of coconut husk fiber at 450°C

Phase 2: Assessing the Impact of Biochar at Different Temperatures on the Physical and Chemical Properties of Experimental Formulas

Methodology:

Samples of grey soil were taken from the experimental fields (previously planted with peanuts). Soil sampling method: collected from the surface to a depth of 15cm.

Biochar at different temperature levels was mixed with grey soil and placed in plastic trays measuring 70cm x 45cm x 20cm. The application rate was 3 tons of biochar per hectare, equivalent to 94.5g of biochar per tray.

Experimental Formulas:

Formula 1 (K1-Control): T1 + Grey soil

Formula 2 (K2-Control): T2 + Grey soil

Formula 3 (K3-Control): T3 + Grey soil

Formula 4 (K4-Control): T4 + Grey soil

Formula 5 (K5-Control): T5 + Grey soil

Formula 6 (K6-Control): T6 + Grey soil

After mixing, the soil samples were placed outdoors for 21 days (from September-1-2021, to September-21-2021). The experimental samples were subjected entirely to natural environmental conditions and had no human interference.

Phase 3: Analysis of the Physical and Chemical Properties of Grey Soil Before and After the Experiment.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Biochar is a carbon-rich material derived from biomass and contains significant amounts of elements including Carbon (C), Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), Calcium oxide (CaO), Magnesium (Mg), and Silicon (Si). The ratio of these elements in biochar depends on the biomass feedstock used for biochar production as well as the pyrolysis conditions such as temperature and heating time.

The effect of pyrolysis temperature on the nutrient ratio in biochar derived from coconut husk fiber.

Table 1

The impact of pyrolysis temperature on the nutrient ratio in biochar derived from coconut coir

Formula	C (%)	N (%)	P ₂ O ₅ (%)	K ₂ O (%)	CaO (%)	MgO (%)	SiO ₂ (%)
T1	38,0	0,92	0,50	1,54	0,28	0,13	2,34
T2	39,4	0,78	0,43	1,75	0,28	0,17	2,33
T3	43,2	0,63	0,39	2,01	0,29	0,28	2,32
T4	50,2	0,57	0,33	2,37	0,26	0,29	2,31
T5	60,5	0,52	0,22	2,42	0,22	0,22	2,34
T6	68,6	0,57	0,15	2,54	0,24	0,29	2,33

Impact of pyrolysis temperature on carbon content in biochar

As the temperature increases from T1 to T6, the carbon content in biochar increases from 38% to 68.6%. This indicates that the pyrolysis process at higher temperatures can produce more carbon in the composition of biochar. This can be explained as follows: Higher temperatures can increase the rate of pyrolysis reaction of organic materials, facilitating the rapid formation of biochar. The pyrolysis process vaporizes most other elements while leaving carbon in the charcoal particles.

Impact of pyrolysis temperature on total nitrogen content in biochar

Temperature plays a crucial role in the production of biochar from coconut husk fiber and affects the total nitrogen content in the final product. From the data, we observe that as the pyrolysis temperature increases from T1 to T3, the nitrogen content decreases from

0.92% to 0.63%. This indicates that the pyrolysis process at higher temperatures can reduce the nitrogen content in biochar.

At higher temperatures (T4-T6), we observe inconsistent changes in nitrogen content. The data shows a variation from 0.57% (T4) to 0.57% (T6), which may be due to the complexity of chemical processes occurring in the pyrolysis environment at these temperatures.

From the experiment, we can conclude that: High-temperature pyrolysis of biochar leads to faster decomposition of organic compounds, including nitrogen-containing compounds. This reduces the total nitrogen content of biochar as nitrogen-containing compounds evaporate, convert to more stable forms, or transform into gases such as ammonia (NH₃) or nitrogen oxides (NO_x).

Impact of pyrolysis temperature on total P₂O₅ content in biochar

Temperature plays a crucial role in determining the total phosphorus pentoxide (P₂O₅) content in biochar derived from coconut husk fiber. During pyrolysis,

volatile compound release and organic matter transformation occur. Higher temperatures typically lead to more decomposition and stronger evaporation of organic compounds, including phosphorus-containing compounds. This explains the decrease in total P_2O_5 content as the temperature increases from 200°C to 450°C.

Impact of pyrolysis temperature on total K_2O content in biochar

Temperature affects the mechanism of potassium retention in biochar. Higher temperatures result in greater carbonization processes and the formation of biochar with higher surface area and greater porosity. These characteristics impact the adsorption and retention of potassium ions on the biochar surface, affecting the overall K_2O content. Therefore, while the total K_2O content accounts for only 1.54% at a pyrolysis temperature of 200°C, it increases to 2.54% when the temperature rises to 450°C.

Impact of pyrolysis temperature on CaO content in biochar

When increasing the temperature from 200°C to 450°C, the CaO content in biochar undergoes some changes but not significantly. During pyrolysis, different temperatures will result in various by-products. The pyrolysis process involves complex kinetics, and some reactions reach equilibrium at lower temperatures. Therefore, increasing the pyrolysis temperature from

200°C to 450°C does not cause significant changes in CaO content.

Impact of pyrolysis temperature on MgO content in biochar

During the pyrolysis of biochar, temperature plays a crucial role in influencing the chemical composition of the final product, including the MgO (magnesium oxide) content. The experiment has shown:

- Increase from 200°C to 250°C: This temperature increase may induce reactions or pyrolysis processes to produce MgO from auxiliary reactions. This leads to an increase in MgO content.

- Increase from 300°C to 450°C: Within this range, it is possible that a point has been reached where the reactions or processes producing MgO have reached their maximum or equilibrium. Therefore, although the temperature continues to rise, the MgO content does not change significantly, indicating stability.

Impact of pyrolysis temperature on SiO_2 content in biochar

Similar to MgO , when the pyrolysis temperature increases from 250°C to 450°C, the SiO_2 content in biochar changes insignificantly. This can be explained by understanding that reactions in the pyrolysis process have their own kinetics, and there may be a certain temperature threshold at which the reactions reach equilibrium. Once this equilibrium is reached, changes in temperature no longer significantly affect the SiO_2 content.

Table 2

Impact of biochar on soil chemical properties

Formula	pH_{KCl}	OC total (%)	N total (%)	P_2O_5 total (%)	K_2O total (%)	P_2O_5 available (mg/100g)	K_2O available (mg/100g)	CEC (equivalent liter /100g)
K1	5,1	0,98	0,2	0,22	0,07	82,9	3,8	4,2
K2	5,8	1,01	0,24	0,28	0,08	83,7	4,2	4,8
K3	5,6	0,89	0,27	0,23	0,09	90,3	4,4	5,2
K4	5,7	1,21	0,28	0,25	0,08	84,7	4,7	4,9
K5	5,6	0,94	0,32	0,29	0,09	92,3	4,9	5,1
K6	5,8	1,29	0,32	0,25	0,06	87,6	5,2	4,6

Applying biochar to grey soil can affect the soil pH, especially in cases where the soil is highly acidic as described. Typically, biochar contains abundant organic matter, especially humic and fulvic acids, capable of interacting with ions in the soil and influencing pH.

When biochar is applied to soil, the organic matter in biochar can interact with hydroxide (OH^-) or hydronium (H_3O^+) ions in the soil, altering the acid-base balance. This can lead to changes in soil pH. In this case, applying the 6 biochar formulas has increased the soil pH from 5.1 to approximately 5.6 - 5.8.

This change can be explained by the enhancement of microbial activity in the soil due to the application of biochar, contributing to the decomposition of organic matter and the release of nutrients. As a result, these processes can generate reaction products that interact with soil ions and cause pH changes.

When applying biochar to grey soil, it alters the total organic carbon (OC) in the soil. In this experiment, before application, the total OC was 0.98%. After applying 6 different formulas of biochar, the total OC in the soil underwent changes as shown in Table 2. Formula 6 (OC 1.29%) showed the highest increase rate, at

31.63%. This can be explained by this formula containing a large amount of organic matter, including organic compounds capable of strong interaction and producing positive reaction products when added to the soil. This significantly increased the total OC in the soil after using this formula.

Overall, all biochar formulas increased the total nitrogen content in the soil, with increases ranging from 20% to 60%. Formulas 4 and 5 showed the highest increase, reaching 60%. This can be explained by the ability of biochar to directly or indirectly supply nitrogen by stimulating microbial activity in the soil. Microorganisms can decompose organic matter in biochar and release nitrogen into the soil. Additionally, biochar can improve soil structure, enhance water and nutrient retention, effectively increasing the total nitrogen content.

All biochar formulas increased the total P_2O_5 content in the soil, with increases ranging from 4.55% to 45.45%. Formula 5 showed the highest increase, reaching 45.45%. This can be explained by biochar's ability to improve the retention and supply of phosphorus to crops. Biochar can absorb and retain nutrients, reduce

leaching, and enhance the availability of phosphorus in the soil. Organic matter and microorganisms in biochar can also help break down poorly soluble phosphorus compounds, effectively increasing the total P_2O_5 content in the soil. However, as the pyrolysis temperature increases from 200°C to 400°C, the total P_2O_5 content tends to increase, but when reaching a pyrolysis temperature of 450°C, the total P_2O_5 content tends to decrease.

The experiment showed that all biochar formulas increased the CEC of the soil, with increases ranging

from 9.52% to 23.81%. Formula 2 showed the highest increase, reaching 23.81%. Biochar can improve the CEC of the soil due to its porous structure and large surface area, helping to retain nutrient cations such as calcium, magnesium, and potassium. This improves the soil's nutrient retention capacity, allowing crops to absorb nutrients more efficiently. Furthermore, biochar can positively impact soil microbial activity, contributing to the improvement of soil structure and cation exchange capacity.

Table 3

Impact of biochar on soil physical properties

Formula	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Particle Density (g/cm ³)	Porosity (%)
K1	1,21	2,5	56,7
K2	1,05	2,40	60,2
K3	1,08	2,42	60,5
K4	1,09	2,44	61,4
K5	1,04	2,39	59,6
K6	1,06	2,40	60,2

Bulk density is an important indicator that reflects the density of soil, meaning the mass of soil per unit volume. Before applying biochar, the bulk density of the soil was 1.21 g/cm³. After applying 6 formulas, the bulk density decreased, ranging from 1.04 g/cm³ to 1.09 g/cm³. This indicates that the application of biochar has positively impacted soil dispersion and water retention capacity.

The reduction in bulk density can have several benefits for crops. Firstly, reducing bulk density enhances soil aeration, improves air and water circulation in the soil, allowing crops easier access to nutrients and water. Secondly, low bulk density also reduces pressure on the root system of plants, helping to develop a stronger root system and more efficient nutrient and water absorption.

Particle density is an index indicating the mass of a unit volume of soil, meaning the amount of material in each unit space of soil. Before applying biochar, the particle density was 2.5 g/cm³. After applying 6 formulas, the particle density decreased, ranging from 2.39 g/cm³ to 2.44 g/cm³. This indicates that the application of biochar has positively impacted soil dispersion and improved soil structure.

Reducing particle density brings many benefits to crops. Firstly, reducing particle density creates a better soil environment for the root system of crops, helping roots to develop stronger and have easier access to nutrients and water. Secondly, low particle density also improves air and water circulation in the soil, helping crops enhance nutrient and water absorption from the soil.

Soil porosity is an index indicating the proportion of void space in the soil compared to the total volume of soil. Before applying biochar, the soil porosity was 56.7%. After applying 6 formulas, soil porosity increased, ranging from 59.6% to 61.4%. This indicates that the application of biochar has increased the void space in the soil, improving soil structure and water drainage capacity.

Increasing soil porosity can bring many benefits to crops. Firstly, increased porosity provides void space for the root system of crops to grow, allowing roots easier access to nutrients and water in the soil. Secondly, increasing porosity also improves soil aeration and water drainage, helping to prevent waterlogging and improve the resilience of crops to both flooding and drought conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

When increasing the pyrolysis temperature, the carbon content in biochar increases from 38% to 68.6%. The high-temperature pyrolysis process generates more carbon due to the increased reaction rate.

As the pyrolysis temperature increases, the nitrogen content decreases from 0.92% to 0.63% at higher temperatures (from T1 to T3). At higher temperatures (T4-T6), the variation in nitrogen content is not consistent. High-temperature pyrolysis reduces the nitrogen content because nitrogen compounds evaporate or transform into gases such as ammonia or nitrogen oxides.

Increasing the pyrolysis temperature typically leads to a decrease in total P_2O_5 content but an increase in total K_2O content. The content of other oxides such as CaO, MgO, SiO₂ may change insignificantly or inconsistently at different temperature levels.

Applying biochar can increase the pH and organic content in soil due to the interaction of organic compounds in biochar with ions in the soil.

Biochar application can reduce bulk density, particle density, and increase soil porosity, improving soil structure and water drainage capacity. Decreasing bulk and particle density can create a better environment for plant root systems and enhance nutrient and water absorption from the soil.

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